

***Rubus hoplotheca* A.Beek & D.P.Mercier, a replacement name for *Rubus radulooides* (W.M.Rogers) J.W.White (Rosaceae)**

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ABSTRACT. – It appeared that the name *Rubus radulooides* (W.M.Rogers) J.W.White is a later homonym of *R. radulooides* (F.Aesch.) Neuman, and consequently illegitimate. *Rubus hoplotheca* A.Beek & D.P.Mercier is published as a replacement name. *Rubus norvegicus* H.E. Weber & A.Pederson is a superfluous later synonym of *R. radulooides* (F.Aesch.) Neuman.

SAMENVATTING. – *Rubus hoplotheca*, een nieuwe naam voor *R. radulooides*. De naam *Rubus radulooides* (W.M.Rogers) J.W.White bleek een later homoniem van *R. radulooides* (F.Aesch.) Neuman, en dus illegitiem. De naam *R. hoplotheca* A.Beek & D.P.Mercier is als vervanging gegeven. *Rubus norvegicus* H.E.Weber & A.Pederson is een overbodig later synoniem van *R. radulooides* (F.Aesch.) Neuman.

RÉSUMÉ. – *Rubus hoplotheca*, un nouveau nom pour *R. radulooides*. Le nom *Rubus radulooides* (W.M.Rogers) J.W.White est un homonyme postérieur à *R. radulooides* (F.Aesch.) Neuman, et est en conséquence illégitime. *R. hoplotheca* A.Beek & D.P.Mercier est publié ici en tant que nom de remplacement. *Rubus norvegicus* H.E.Weber & A.Pederson est un synonyme superflu plus récent de *R. radulooides* (F.Aesch.) Neuman.

During the preparation of the new version of the Genus *Rubus* L. for the new edition of the *Nouvelle Flore de la Belgique/Flora van België* several names must be corrected when compared with the previous edition. Most of these names were previously validly published but their identity was discovered only recently. The argumentations of these name changes can be published after the publication of the new edition of the flora. However, one name, *R. radulooides* (W.M.Rogers) J.W.White is illegitimate but no other synonym is available to replace it. Because it is undesirable to use illegitimate or even unpublished names in the flora, it was decided to publish a replacement name with priority.

It appeared that the name *Rubus radulooides* (W.M.Rogers) J.W.White (1901: 131) is a later homonym of *R. radulooides* (F.Aesch.) Neuman (1888: 60). Aeschoug described a *Rubus corylifolius* var. *radulooides* (Aeschoug 1876: 1168), which Neuman (1888: 60) raised to the species rank. It is a taxon of the section *Corylifolii* and identical with *R. norvegicus* H.E.Weber & A.Pederson (Weber 1991: 197). Weber & Pederson cite *Rubus corylifolius* var. *radulooides* Aeschoug as a synonym. Although they do not refer to Neuman (1888), the type of *R. radulooides* (F.Aesch.) Neuman is included in the protologue because of the citation of its basionym and an explicit reference. Consequently *R. norvegicus* is a superfluous later synonym of it (art. 52.2).

Because Neuman's publication is earlier than that of *R. radulooides* (W.M.Rogers) J.W.White, the latter is illegitimate and in need of another name. Weber (1986: 306) is of the opinion that *R. radulispinus* Mayer (1931: 151) would be a later synonym. Unfortunately the lectotype that he selected (Auf einer Waldblöße zw. Fecking und Toign, 29.6.1921, *Mayer 5130*, REG) could, in spite of efforts by the curator of REG, Peter Poschod, not be traced. However, from the protologue it is clear that it cannot be the same taxon as *R. radulooides*. The characteristics of curved spines and narrow white petals do not correspond with that species. The locality near Regensburg (Bavaria) where it was collected is also rather far away from the Atlantic distribution of *R. radulooides*. Weber (1986: 308; 2005: 96) mentions he found the taxon at the locus classicus, but as the collection date was in September, the specimens most probably did not have petals in order to confirm their coloration and form.

Another species which is of interest is *R. heteracanthus* P.J.Müll. (Müller 1859: 102; lectotypus, designated by Matzke-Hajek 2001: Remigiusberg, près de Cusel, 18.7.1858, *Stiefelhagen 1390*, STR; isotype in BORD) which has also similarity to *R. radulooides*. However, also this likeness is only at first glance. The prickles on the axis of the lectotype are more numerous, more equal, strongly compressed and yellowish, not slender and purple as with *R. radulooides*; gland-tipped acicles are almost lacking,

and the prickles on the petiolule are hooked; the inflorescence has only very short stipitate glands; the leaves are adaxillary hairy and the flowers white.

No other synonyms are known. Consequently a new name is required, which is published here.

Rubus hoplotheca A.Beek & D.P.Mercier, nom. nov. pro *Rubus raduloides* (W.M.Rogers) J.W.White, *Proceed. Bristol Nat. Soc.* 9: 131 (1901), non *R. raduloides* (F.Aesch) Neuman, *Bot. Not.* 1888: 60 (1888).

Basionyme of *Rubus raduloides* (W.M.Rogers) J.W.White: *Rubus anglosaxonicus* Gelert var. *raduloides* W.M.Rogers, *J. Bot.* 30: 269 (1892).

Lectotype (designated by Weber 1974): Piddle Wood, Sturminster, Newton, Dorset, 22.7.1890, *Rogers s.n.* (BM).

The epithet 'hoplotheca' ('arsenal') refers to the great variation in prickles of the plant.

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